

Numerical modelling of bacteriologic impacts in the Laïta estuary (France)

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Abstract— The Laïta estuary is located on the French Atlantic coast. Degraded for a long time by different sources (agriculture, industry, waste water treatment plant (WWTP) outfall...), the bacteriological quality of Laïta has improved, confirmed by a recent decree allowing mussels farming downstream the estuary.

However, local authorities wish to increase knowledges on contamination sources in order to decrease drastically the main bacteriological releases in the watershed.

In this context, a three-dimensional model has been set up to better understand the behaviour and impact of the various sources of contamination. The study also aims to prioritise contamination flows and evaluate a series of proposals for improvements. The model Telemac 3D is set up in order to represent maritime and river processes. Various data allow calibrating and validating the model hydraulically.

In order to model faecal coliform concentrations, it is necessary or even essential to study the mortality of bacteria. Classically, a first order of decay law is used where a value of T90 is imposed (duration to obtain 90% mortality). However, for an estuarine problem where salinity and temperature in particular may change, the use of a constant T90 value may be incorrect. In fact, the T90 bacteria vary from a few hours to a few days, but for the majority of the hydrodynamic conditions, the transit of bacteria from the river waters to the marine waters (which can greatly increase the mortality rate of bacteria) lasts less than one tidal cycle.

It was therefore decided to use a formula [5] to calculate the degradation coefficient (k) bacteria based on key parameters affecting bacteria mortality such as salinity, temperature, depth and light intensity.

For the calibration scenarios, the flows imposed at the affluent borders are either the result of monitoring survey or from parametric analysis. Effluent discharges from WWTP outfalls and any accidental pollution are also included in the modelling. They are represented by a concentration of micro-bacteria and a characteristic discharge.

This paper presents firstly the calibration of the numerical bacteriological dispersion model, the prioritization of faecal coliform fluxes, a brief analysis on impacts and a discussion on possible solutions to improve the bacteriological quality.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Laïta estuary specification

The Laïta is a coastal river in South Brittany (French Atlantic coast) formed by the confluence of the Isole and the Ellé in the city of Quimperlé, and extends for about fifteen kilometres south until its mouth (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Laita estuary situation [7]

The Ellé affluent flows on 71 km draining a watershed of 603 km². The smaller Isole drains a 226 km² watershed, located on the western side of the Ellé, and meanders along a 48 km linear. Laïta River receives the waters of the two previous rivers and extends over 17 km draining its own watershed of an area of 88 km².

Downstream of the confluence Ellé/ Isole, the Laïta receives the waters of the following main rivers: the Dourdu (RB - right bank), the Frou (RB), the Keryhuel (LB - left bank), the Saint-Michel (LB) and the Quinquis (RB). Smaller rivers are also present but they will not be studied here.

The coastline is subject to a semi-diurnal tide with a range of about 2 m during neap tide, 4.1 m during spring tide and 5.5 m for the highest astronomical tides.

The characteristic flows of these rivers are given in the Table 1.

TABLE 1. CHARACTERISTIC FLOWS OF THE MAIN RIVERS

River	Surface	Q_{\min}	Q_{median}	Q_{10}	Q_{100}
Ellé	603 km ²	1 m ³ /s	9,5 m ³ /s	110 m ³ /s	330 m ³ /s
Isole	226 km ²	0,5 m ³ /s	4,3 m ³ /s	51 m ³ /s	200 m ³ /s
Laita (downstream Quimperlé)	832 km ²	2 m ³ /s	13,9 m ³ /s	160 m ³ /s	> 500 m ³ /s

As the estuary is subject to an oceanic climate, there is a significant seasonal variation between winter and summer period.

The limit of the dynamic tide is at Quimperlé. However, the tide influences the water levels upstream only in the context of moderate flood flows. In high-flood conditions, the influence of astronomical tide on the upstream section is negligible.

The position of the salinity front varies during the tidal cycle, also depending on the coefficient and fluvial flow. Measurements and modelling results of this study show that the salinity front could reach 8 km upstream and during periods of high river discharge, the salt water mass is blocked at the river mouth.

B. Main sources of contamination

For this study, only *Escherichia Coli* (*E. Coli*) is studied as a tracer of water quality. Within the Laita watershed, various sources of contamination are identified.

Firstly, the percentage of the population connected to a collective sanitation network was estimated at 65%. These networks are treated by 3 waste water treatment plants (WWTP) which have a direct outfall in the river. Two are located directly downstream Quimperlé and reject a significant concentration of bacteria. The third outfall is located at the mouth and is equipped of Membrane Bioreactor Module (BRM) treatment which allows a low concentration discharge (< 250 CFU/100ml).

Beside these installations, more than 1700 non-collective sanitation facilities were enumerated in the sub-watershed of the Laita.

Finally, 70 farms are listed on the study area, representing 3,785 ha of agricultural area in use. Diagnostics are currently realized to evaluate conformities of these different exploitations.

Other sources of contamination can be also listed, like sediments, recreational activities, avifauna...

C. Water quality issues

On the Laita area, main issues on water quality concerns bathing waters, mussel farming and nautical activities like kayak.

Different threshold relative to French regulation exist and give a corresponding class of quality. Overtaking a critical threshold can conduct to use restriction or interdiction.

II. BACTERIOLOGICAL MONITORING

To control the water quality in the Laita, many monitoring networks have been setup over the last 3 decades ([6], [9], and [2]). For this study, we used monitoring focused on main affluent which contains discharge measurements. We also have data on WWTP outlets (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Location of monitoring points. Blue circles corresponds to measurements at affluent downstream, pink stars corresponds to WWTP outlets and red triangles corresponds to river surveys.

TABLE 2. CHARACTERISTIC FLOWS OF THE MAIN RIVERS

Bacteriological fluxes (CFU/s)	Mean			Percentile 95		
	Global	Wet	Dry	Global	Wet	Dry
Isole (IS2)	1.7E+07	7.6E+07	3.4E+06	1.9E+09	4.3E+09	8.1E+07
Ellé (EL2)	2.9E+07	1.2E+08	6.2E+06	2.6E+09	9.2E+09	8.0E+07
Dourdu (DOUR)	1.2E+07	2.1E+07	5.9E+06	5.8E+08	6.5E+08	5.5E+08
WWTP 3	1.1E+07	/	/	2.7E+08	/	/
WWTP 2	4.8E+06	/	/	5.7E+07	/	/
Froot (FR)	5.3E+05	6.7E+06	4.2E+04	7.4E+08	2.0E+09	6.9E+07
Keryhuel (KER)	4.9E+05	1.8E+06	4.5E+04	2.3E+07	2.4E+07	3.8E+05
St Michel (STM)	3.9E+05	7.4E+05	1.3E+05	2.4E+07	2.5E+07	5.0E+05
Quinquis (QUIN)	6.5E+05	1.6E+06	1.8E+05	5.9E+07	9.7E+07	5.0E+06
WWTP 1	2.8E+03	/	/	3.5E+04	/	/

The table 2 gives the bacteriological fluxes for the main sources of contamination of Laïta for wet period, dry period and global measurement period. The table gives mean and percentile results.

Measurements (E. Coli concentrations and discharge) are realized downstream of each affluent. We called a “dry period” when no rain was detected in the watershed during the 10 preceding days and “wet period” when there is a global river discharge increase due to rain in the last 24 hours.

Regarding the Figure 2, sources of contamination are surveyed but there are also measurement points along the river between the Laïta river mouth and Quimperlé (LA01 to LA12).

III. MODEL SETUP

A. Computational grid

The computational grid extents from Quimperlé to ocean (figure below) in order to well represent mixing of ocean and river processes.

The grid is composed by 31 500 nodes and about 59 000 triangles. The mesh sizes range from 250 m offshore to 3 m around the Laïta bridge piers. It was built in order to obtain a reasonable computation time on a basic computer [1]. However, at the narrowest minor bed, the width of the bed is represented by 4 to 5 triangular meshes. However, this mesh resolution allows fulfilling the objective of the study that is to represent the plume behaviour at the estuary scale.

Figure 3. Representation of the computational grid

3D discretisation is made of 5 sigma plans. The distribution of the plans on the talweg is shown on the figure below.

Figure 4. Vertical discretisation on river talweg.

B. Faecal decay law

The mathematical formulations of decay processes for E.coli, in this case, used as the indicator bacteria, are described below. Biodegradation is according to [8] defined as the biologically catalysed reduction in complexity of chemical compounds. Furthermore, it is described as the process by which organic substances are broken down from larger to smaller compounds by microbial organisms.[8]. The general degradation of faeces indicators such as E. Coli is assumed to follow a general exponential first-order model [3].

$$C(t) = C(t = 0) * e^{(-k*t)}$$

Where, C is the concentration of organism, t is the time and k is the decay rate coefficient at 20 °C.

The degradation rate coefficient can be described in several different ways.

The method for calculating k is based on information concerning water temperature, light intensity and salinity. In this case, an infinite oxygen supply is assumed [5].

The decay parameter k consists of decay contributions from light respectively dark conditions and is described in equation below.

$$k = K_m + K_L * I_z \quad (1)$$

Where, K_m is the decay contribution when dark conditions, K_L is the decay contribution when light conditions, I_z is the light intensity at depth z.

The decay contribution, when dark conditions, is calculated with equation below.

$$K_m = a_T * T - k_{m0} \quad (2)$$

Where, a_T is the temperature dependency constant for dark reaction, T is the actual water temperature and k_{m0} is the initial coliform decay rate constant for dark reaction. It is only valid between 4 and 24 °C.

$$K_L = S_m * \frac{(b_T * T + K_{L0})}{a * S_m - (\frac{1}{a}) * S} \quad (3)$$

Where, S is the actual salinity, S_m is the reference salinity constant, a is the correction for salinity constant, b_T is the temperature dependency constant for light reaction and K_{L0} is the initial coliform decay rate for light reaction. This equation is only valid between 12 and 34 °C [5].

The light intensity at depth z, I_z can be described by Lambert-Beer's law.

$$I_z = I_0 * e^{-\mu * z} \quad (4)$$

Where, I_0 is the light intensity at the water surface, μ is the extinction coefficient and z is the depth to the contamination. The extinction coefficient can be decided from the secchi depth, SD. For the determination of μ , it is assumed that the secchi depth corresponds to the depth at which 15% of the

light radiation remains. This ratio may, however, range from about 10% up to 25% depending on the area.

$$\mu = -\ln\left(\frac{0.15}{SD}\right) \quad (5)$$

To sum up, the degradation of E.coli can be described in a single equation:

$$C_{E.coli} = C_{E.coli 0} * e^{\left(-\left((a_T * T - k_{m0}) + \left(S_m * \frac{(b_T * T + K_{L0})}{a * S_m - \left(\frac{1}{a}\right) * S}\right) * (I_0 * e^{-\left(-\ln\left(\frac{0.15}{SD}\right)\right) * z})\right) * t\right)} \quad (6)$$

This equation for degradation of E. coli is only subject to decay, and the decay processes describing the variations of the bacteria in time and space are dependent on external factors such as salinity, light influx and water temperature.

Moreover, this formula has been already implemented in a Telemac 3D fortran file [9].

C. Input

On the oceanic part, the model is first forced at its borders with a global tidal model TPXO [4] to take into account the variation of currents and water levels related to the astronomical tide.

The main affluents of the Laita are taken into account. A discharge and an E. Coli concentration can be applied.

Effluent discharges from WWTP outfalls and any accidental pollution are also included in the modelling. They are represented by a concentration of micro-bacteria and a characteristic discharge.

A model is then launched with no bacterial concentration as initial condition. Contaminated water will mix with sea water within a few tidal cycles.

D. Hydraulic model validation

Various hydraulic conditions were observed during February 2017 with an ADCP moored downstream of Quimperlé [1]. Cycles of spring and neap tides with a period of low flows (15 m³/s) and a period of flood (Q > 50 m³/s) could be recorded. This campaign was therefore very useful for calibrating the model for different hydraulic conditions.

Comparisons between model and measurements show a good correlation with water level and velocities for all measured conditions.

Different monitoring has allowed also validating salinity dispersion model. Comparison shows that the distribution of salinity at the scale of sampling is well represented by the numerical model for the different campaigns studied. The model results are relatively close to the measurements.

E. Bacteriological model calibration

Once it has been ensured that numerical model can represent all the hydraulic conditions measured, a calibration of the bacteriological dispersion model is carried out. Four surveys have been selected representing different hydraulic and tidal conditions (see Table 3) and for which main measurements upstream are available.

For each sources of contaminant, discharges (Q) and E. Coli concentrations have been settled according to measurements (see Table 4).

For WWTP 1 & 2, discharges and concentrations have been estimated with monthly mean due to a lack of measurements within these surveys. For WWTP 3, concentration values can be very high and then will show influence of this outfall in the estuary. For little affluents, there were no data available so it has been decided to not include them as they represent a minor part from contaminant sources.

TABLE 3. HYDRAULIC AND TIDAL CONDITIONS FOR THE 4 SURVEYS SELECTED FOR NUMERICAL MODEL CALIBRATION.

Survey #	date	Q Laita (m ³ /s)	Tidal coefficient
1	21/07/2011	2.95	64
2	09/04/2015	9.72	75
3	26/04/2012	63	65
4	15/12/2014	22.4	38

TABLE 4. DISCHARGES (M³/S) AND BACTERIAL CONCENTRATIONS (CFU / 100ML) FOR EACH SOURCES FOR MODEL CALIBRATION.

Survey #	1	2	3	4
Conditions	Summer - Dry	Winter - Dry	Winter - Rain	Winter - Rain
Ellé	Q: 1.9 [E. Coli]: 78	Q: 6.67 [E. Coli]: 38	Q: 42 [E. Coli]: 2000	Q: 15.2 [E. Coli]: 403
Isole	Q: 1.05 [E. Coli]: 1000	Q: 3.05 [E. Coli]: 1000	Q: 21 [E. Coli]: 8900	Q: 7.2 [E. Coli]: 500
Dourdu	Q: 0.07 [E. Coli]: 14000	Q: 0.1 [E. Coli]: 5840	Q: 0.5 [E. Coli]: 2700	Q: 0.5 [E. Coli]: 2990
Froust	Q: 0.015 [E. Coli]: 510	Q: 0.04 [E. Coli]: 1749	Q: 0.25 [E. Coli]: 8300	Q: 0.25 [E. Coli]: 457
WWTP 3	Q: 0.04 [E. Coli]: 1 700 000	Q: 0.04 [E. Coli]: 1 015 000	Q: 0.04 [E. Coli]: 620 000	Q: 0.04 [E. Coli]: 920
WWTP 2	Q: 0.06 [E. Coli]: 32 000	Q: 0.06 [E. Coli]: 32 000	Q: 0.06 [E. Coli]: 32 000	Q: 0.06 [E. Coli]: 32 000
WWTP 1	Q: 0.02 [E. Coli]: 17	Q: 0.02 [E. Coli]: 17	Q: 0.02 [E. Coli]: 17	Q: 0.02 [E. Coli]: 17

Figure 5 show E. Coli concentration model results of vertical Laita view from Quimperlé (right) to river mouth (left) for different moments of the tidal cycle (survey #1)

Figure 5. E Coli concentration model results of vertical Laita view from Quimperlé (right) to river mouth (left) for a) High tide (HT), b) HT-3h, c) Low tide (LT) and d) LT-3h.

Model results show the effluent dispersion according to tide with higher concentrations upstream decreasing until the

river mouth. The contribution of bacterial flow from the Froot River can be observed (LA07) with its plume going toward Quimperlé during flow inversion at high tide.

In all surveys investigated, a general decrease of bacterial concentration can be observed upstream to river mouth as the salinity of water column is higher.

As the journey of bacteria is relatively fast inside estuary (generally one tidal cycle depending on tide range and river discharge), effect of gradient salinity is very important on bacteria decay rate. Thus, model calibration was mainly focused on "a" parameter in equation 3. This parameter has firstly been set according to [10]. This value has a significant effect on bacterial mortality when mixing to sea water. Tuning this parameter with the four simulations based on surveys exposed above yield to a satisfying compromise (see Table 5).

TABLE 5. COMPARISON OF E. COLI CONCENTRATIONS (CFU/100ML) BETWEEN MODEL RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS DURING MODEL CALIBRATION PHASE.

Survey #	LA12	LA11	LA10	LA08	LA07	LA05	LA03	LA01	
1	obs.	8 300	6 600	6 100	1 400	510	460	46	15
	Model	2 000	11 000	2 760	75	200	120	3	1
2	obs.	728	1 494	1 104	2 779	1 749	858	94	15
	Model	789	3 400	2 350	1 450	1 130	650	81	20
3	obs.	8 300	11 000	6 100	7 700	8 300	11 000	8 900	6 100
	Model	3 880	4 180	3 900	3 610	4 830	3 430	2 910	2 520
4	obs.	465	480	434	563	457	633	919	415
	Model	650	670	590	470	410	350	210	130

Overall comparisons of model results with in-situ measurements are close. However, survey #3 and a few points of comparison give significant differences. Table 6 gives the differences between model and measurements.

TABLE 6. DIFFERENCES (CFU/100ML) BETWEEN MODEL RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS DURING MODEL CALIBRATION PHASE.

Survey #	LA12	LA11	LA10	LA08	LA07	LA05	LA03	LA01
1	6E+03	-4E+03	3E+03	1E+03	3E+02	3E+02	4E+01	1E+01
2	-6E+01	-2E+03	-1E+03	1E+03	6E+02	2E+02	1E+01	-5E+00
3	4E+03	7E+03	2E+03	4E+03	3E+03	8E+03	6E+03	4E+03
4	-2E+02	-2E+02	-2E+02	9E+01	5E+01	3E+02	7E+02	3E+02

For survey #3, the model underestimates concentrations by 10^3 along the estuary. This campaign presents the highest discharge and probably, the measurement protocol for this high hydraulic condition is debatable.

Around LA12, LA11 and LA10, differences can also reach 10^3 . It can be caused by the estimation of bacterial flow of WWTP 1&2.

There are also uncertainties of contamination supply on a few minor affluents like in survey #4 around LA03 with St-Michel (STM) affluent.

Temperatures during surveys #2 and #3 are just below 10°C which is outside the range of validity for equation 5.

Otherwise, general differences between model and measurement are on range of 10^1 and 10^2 which is acceptable according to the several assumptions made in this model and to the bacterial measurements uncertainties.

Moreover, the model allows well representing the high decay rate in the mixing sea water transition as in survey #2 after LA05.

IV. MODEL APPLICATION

A. Mean conditions

In order to characterize the general behaviour of water quality in the estuary, eight scenarios were built depending on river discharge, contaminant flow, water temperature and tidal range. These scenarios are described in the table 7. They have been built according to measurements almost on 10 years of monitoring.

TABLE 7. DEFINITION OF 8 SCENARIOS TO CHARACTERIZE WATER QUALITY BEHAVIOUR IN THE LAITA ESTUARY.

Hydraulic condition	Q_{River} Winter $T_{\text{water}} = 9^\circ\text{C}$		Q_{River} Summer $T_{\text{water}} = 19^\circ\text{C}$	
	Dry period	Wet period	Dry period	Wet period
Contaminant flow				
Light intensity	$I_0 = 720\ 000$	$I_0 = 200\ 000$	$I_0 = 5\ 700\ 000$	$I_0 = 1\ 000\ 000$
Neap tide	Scénario 1	Scénario 3	Scénario 5	Scénario 7
Spring tide	Scénario 2	Scénario 4	Scénario 6	Scénario 8

Results are presented in the table 8 as the maximal concentration reached during simulation along the estuary for the 8 simulated scenarios.

TABLE 8. MAXIMAL E. COLI CONCENTRATION INSIDE LAITA ESTUARY FOR THE 8 CHARACTERISTIC SCENARIOS.

Scenario #	LA12	LA11	LA10	LA08	LA07	LA05	LA03	LA01
1	500	754	550	371	260	246	105	25
2	501	862	571	398	254	245	100	26
3	1 840	1 821	1 715	1 556	1 934	1 455	1 233	1 031
4	1 830	1 826	1 719	1 558	1 816	1 492	1 248	1 064
5	686	544	71	56	318	83	2	2
6	666	520	87	61	318	108	16	1
7	1 875	1 713	1 010	426	1 762	417	160	78
8	1 873	1 690	1 002	436	2 152	1 102	535	147

Highest E. Coli concentrations are mainly upstream.

Generally, concentrations change strongly during the tidal cycle and especially for "medium" or "low" flows. The bacterial decay rate is highly dependent on the salinity front behaviour.

For "high" flows (winter in wet period), E. Coli concentrations are relatively constant from upstream to river mouth. The estuary is composed of freshwater along the

estuary, regardless of tide. The bacterial decay rate is therefore lower.

Tide affects only downstream point (from LA08 to LA01). The tidal range is affectless on maximum E. Coli concentration.

For low discharges and mean E. Coli concentration, the area of influence of WWTP or minor affluents is limited.

B. Peak or accidental effluent discharges

River discharge and E. Coli concentration presented in the 8 previous scenarios are based on the median of measurements. Other scenarios were also investigated with percentiles 95 as peak concentration or as accidental discharge.

An example is given below with the precedent scenarios 2 and 8 which are simulated with a WWTP concentration based on percentile 95 (7.10^6 CFU/100ml for WWTP3 and 8.10^5 CFU/100ml for WWTP2). These 2 scenarios, called scenarios 9 and 10 simulate then a peak discharge for these installations. Results are given in Table 9 as maximal concentrations reached inside the estuary and are compared to scenarios 2 and 8.

TABLE 9. MAXIMAL E. COLI CONCENTRATION FOR SCENARIO 9 AND 10 COMPARED TO SCENARIO 2 AND 8 AND RATIO BETWEEN VALUES.

	LA12	LA11	LA10	LA08	LA07	LA05	LA03	LA01
Scenario 2	501	862	571	398	254	245	100	26
Scenario 9	501	9 263	4 942	2 925	1 720	1 739	633	122
ratio 9/2	1	11	9	7	7	7	6	5
Scenario 8	1 873	1 690	1 002	436	2 152	1 102	535	147
Scenario 10	1 873	8 499	4 079	1 543	2 182	1 125	552	151
ratio 10/8	1	5	4	4	1	1	1	1

These results show that during winter and dry weather (scenarios 2 and 9), the influence of WWTP with a 95 percentile is visible until LA01 while in summer and rainy weather (scenarios 8 and 10), it is visible only until LA07, at the confluence with the Froust river. Indeed, this river during rainy period is significantly contaminated due to most likely agriculture activities taken place up to the watershed. Thus, contamination from WWTP close to Quimperlé is mixed downstream with the supply of the Froust River at LA07.

These results allow affirming the role of WWTP on river mouth for specific conditions. This result is important as the river mouth area concentrates the entire mussel farming activities and water bathing quality issues

This exercise is done on each affluent or possible contaminant source in order to classify the stronger bacterial contributors regarding the river mouth issues (see Table 10)

Once this exercise has been done, different solutions has been proposed to decrease contamination for main sources. These solutions encompass for example a tertiary treatment for WWTP, investment on agriculture exploitation, action on non-collective sanitation or rehabilitation works on collective sanitation network.

All these solutions have been also tested with 3D numerical model in order to appreciate effects on the river mouth issues.

TABLE 10. PRIORITIZATION OF MAIN CONTAMINANT SOURCES

SOURCES	Mean flow order	Peak flow order
Isole (IS2)	2	2
Ellé (EL2)	1	1
Dourdu (DOUR)	3	4
WWTP 3	4	5
WWTP 2	5	7
Froust (FR)	7	3
Keryhuél (KER)	8	9
St Michel (STM)	9	8
Quinquis (QUIN)	6	6
WWTP 1	10	10

V. CONCLUSION

To conclude, a numerical tool has been set up to represent bacterial dispersion in the Laïta River based on an equation calculating decay rate of E. coli dependent on external factors such as salinity, light influx and water temperature. The model has been calibrated with 4 in-situ campaigns and gives acceptable correlation. The calibration step showed importance to have a complete set of data and the necessity to take into account salinity effect in an estuary instead of constant decay rate as a T90 law.

Once the numerical tool has been validated, a complete analysis of the estuary and the main contaminant sources have been done to give prioritization and give solutions to improve the general water quality, above all close to the activities issues (mussel farming and bathing water).

REFERENCES

- [1] Acri. Etude hydrologique, hydraulique et hydro-sédimentaire de la Laïta amont – Rapport technique provisoire 2018. réf.: A1523-1317-M-RE2-V1.1. Syndicat Mixte Ellé Isole Laïta.
- [2] Cellules Qualité des Eaux Littorales (CQEL) - Dreal Bretagne, Réseau des estuaires Bretons. Qualité des eaux: Présentation des résultats. Campagne 2012. Juillet 2013.
- [3] Chick H. & Martin C. J. 1908, The Principles Involved in the Standardisation of Disinfectants and the Influence of Organic Matter upon Germicidal Value, The Journal of Hygiene, vol.8:5,p.654–97.
- [4] Egbert, Gary D., and Svetlana Y. Erofeeva. "Efficient inverse modeling of barotropic ocean tides." Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology 19.2 (2002): 183-204.
- [5] Erichsen, A.C., Dannesøe, J.G., Jørgensen, C., Mark, O. and Kaas, H. 2006, Implementation and description of different early warning systems for bathing water quality Original title: Etablering af badevandsprofiler og varslingsystemer i henhold til EU's nye badevandsdirektiv, Danish EPA, Miljøprojekt Nr 1101 (in Danish), <http://www2.mst.dk/udgiv/publikationer/2006/87-7052-126-3/html/heelpubl.htm> [2017-08-30].
- [6] Ifremer (2019). Evaluation de la qualité des zones de production conchylicole. Département 29. Edition 2019. rst.ode.littoral.ler/bo-19-001 03/05/2019.
- [7] In Vivo (2013a). Diagnostic du fonctionnement hydro-sédimentaire de la Laïta. Rapport final. Syndicat Mixte Ellé Isole Laïta.
- [8] Joutey N. T., Bahafid W., Sayel H. & El Ghachtouli N. 2013, Biodegradation: involved Microorganisms and Genetically Engineered Microorganisms, Biodegradation-Life of Science, p.289
- [9] Labocca - SMEIL, Suivi de la qualité bactériologique des eaux du bassin versant Ellé-Isole-Laïta – Année 4 (2015-2016) March 2017.
- [10] Selmeus L. (2017). Dynamic modelling of bathing water quality with biodegradation of Escherichia coli in TELEMAR-3D. Master Thesis TVVR 18/5001.

